

IMPROVING LEGAL AWARENESS AND CULTURE IS THE NEED OF THE TIME

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Abstract. *In this article, it is highlighted that one of the main goals and objectives is to further improve the legal consciousness, legal culture, education, and legal literacy of citizens, to increase the interest of young people in the field of law, and to educate them as a legally mature and mature generation.*

Keywords: *state, law, legal consciousness, legal culture, share, person, decree, society, democracy, policy, norm.*

Based on the age-old traditions, customs, language, religion, and spirit of our people, legal culture serves to inculcate in our minds the feelings of enlightenment and truth, such as honesty and faith, justice and legality, high respect and attention to people, and patience. Therefore, it is a vital necessity to raise the opinion and worldview of people, the legal culture directed to selfless work for our independence. Raising the legal culture and legal awareness of the population, legal education and enlightenment, fundamentally improving the order of legal knowledge in society, deep respect and respect for human rights and freedoms, a sense of obedience to the law in people, knowledge of laws and strict adherence to them Determining the happiness of doing is a necessary requirement of today. [1]

In the process of building a legal democratic state and a just civil society, the main and important task is to form the legal consciousness and legal culture of every citizen. A necessary condition for building a legal state is the unconditional implementation of laws. Uniform and unconditional implementation of laws depends on the attitude of each person to his duty and feeling of responsibility [2]

First of all, it is appropriate to get acquainted with the various definitions of legal consciousness and legal culture given by scientists, among others, Professor Islamov gives the following definition of legal consciousness: , can be defined as a system of legal intuitions, ideas, evaluations, imaginations that express the attitude to obligations, to the desired right and to other legal events".[3]

"Legal consciousness is the sum of views, ideas, and imaginations of people and the whole society in relation to the actual law and legal reality." In his book, legal culture is defined as follows: "Legal culture is the level of the legal system established in society, the level of people's awareness of this legal system, the respect of citizens for the law, the level of enforcement of legal norms, intolerance to those who do not follow the law, obedience to the law. we understand the level" [5]

So, to conclude from the above, being fully aware of the adopted laws, any regulatory legal documents, changes in the field of law, legal awareness as a result of studying and understanding and following them is a legal forms culture. A high level of legal culture is a unique feature of a legal state. In the conditions of the formation of the market economy, increasing the legal culture is considered an important task.

High legal awareness and legal activity of citizens is the foundation of the rule of law and legal state in an enlightened society. Formation of legal awareness of citizens, prevention of violations, and fight against crime is a necessary requirement. In fact, foreign ideas, views, and illegal actions that enter a person with legal immunity from the outside will not have their effect. As a result of socialization, individuals understand the existence of laws such as goodness and justice, human dignity and its protection, and freedom and slavery. Legal literacy and legal maturity will help them to understand "what is good and what is bad for themselves".

After gaining independence in our country, great attention has been paid to increasing the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population. For example, on August 29, 1997, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the "National Program for Improving Legal Culture in Society". In it, the increase in the level of legal culture of the population depends in many ways on the knowledge of the legislative, executive and judicial authorities, the stimulation of the research of the scientific foundations of legal culture, the organization of socio-legal research [6] norm.uz and other issues. reflected. However, due to the change of times and the level of thinking of citizens, the task of updating this national program is being set. In addition, the Presidential decree of February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", adopted on September 7, 2017 "On the distribution of legal information and ensuring its use" on Law, April 13, 2018 Presidential Decree "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Activities of Justice Bodies and Institutions in the Implementation of State Legal Policy", January 9, 2019 "Legal Awareness in Society and it is possible to see the adoption of the Presidential Decree "On Fundamental Improvement of the Legal Culture Improvement System" and other regulatory and legal documents. [7]

Separate public opinion polls are also conducted to determine the level of awareness and participation of the population in legal processes. As an example, in 2017, a public opinion survey on the topic "25th anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was conducted by the Public Opinion Research Center. According to the survey data, the absolute majority of citizens, i.e. 90.5 percent, consider the Constitution of Uzbekistan to be "the main document regulating legal relations in the country", in which the formation of a sovereign state and a just society fundamental principles, commitment to the protection and strengthening of human rights, to the ideals of democracy and social justice, to ensuring the peace of citizens and inter-ethnic harmony. The absolute majority of citizens - 86.3 percent - expressed the opinion that the basic law not only meets the modern requirements of the time, but is also designed for the future. In this survey, the level of awareness of the population about their civil rights was determined. To the question "Do you know your civil rights?", the absolute majority of citizens - 92.6 percent - voted affirmatively. [8] the fact that such social polls are held frequently will greatly help to study the opinion of the population and to eliminate the shortcomings that exist in them.

President Shavkat Mirziyoev, in his speech entitled "Our Parliament should become a school of real democracy, be the initiator and main executor of reforms", critically analyzed the activities of political parties, their parliamentary factions and deputies, and stated the following points: "Improving the work style of deputies, increasing the legal culture of the population through political parties: "It would be a good idea to introduce a new system working in the order of "Center - region - district" [9], because the creation and development of all laws is carried out by deputies. It is necessary and necessary for them to create laws based on the interests of the people and the needs of the people, studying all suggestions and recommendations, deficiencies

among the people. Those who did not say that the system works in the order of "Center-Province-District" for nothing, the changes and additions in any policy will reach from the center to the region, then to the district and other remote areas. who mentioned that such a system should be created taking into account the need. Public participation and activity is important in consistently and widely informing the population about the changes and additions to every law, legal documents in force in our country. It is necessary to effectively use the opportunities of communication technologies, social partnership with state bodies. 10]

In 2019, in order to improve the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, the Presidential Decree "On fundamental improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society" was adopted. In this decree: it is considered one of the most important conditions for ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legality in order to improve legal consciousness and legal culture in the society [11].

In short, legal consciousness and legal culture is a gradual process. The rise of legal culture led to the development of the sense of obedience to the law. Currently, this issue is being raised to the level of state policy, for this purpose it is important to further improve the legal consciousness, legal culture, education, and legal literacy of citizens, to increase the interest of young people in the field of law, and to raise them as a legally mature and competent generation. is one of the goals and objectives. Citizens who know their rights in the society and obey the laws are the foundation of the legal state.

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